

COMPUTER VISION BASED NEUROIMAGE ANALYSIS USING EXTENSIVE FEATURE EXTRACTION AND SELECTION TECHNIQUES FOR BRAIN TUMOR DETECTION: A REVIEW

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DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14357166>

MAZEDAN COMPUTER
ENGINEERING TRANSACTIONS

e-ISSN: 2583-0414

Article id: MCET0402005

Vol.-4, Issue-2

Received: 23 Sep 2023

Revised: 21 Nov 2023

Accepted: 29 Nov 2023

Citation: Khan, F., & Kumar, M. (2023). Computer Vision Based Neuroimage Analysis using Extensive Feature Extraction and Selection Techniques for Brain Tumor Detection: A Review. *Mazedan Computer Engineering Transactions*, 4(2), 19-24.

Abstract

Detection and diagnosis of Brain Tumors (BT) are of the utmost significance aspects in the process of preventative measures and therapeutic planning for patients. The procedure of assessing BT has become substantially more automated and legitimate throughout the time of the inception of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques. These innovations have brought about outstanding improvement. This paper provides a comprehensive review of the most recent research on brain tumor detection and diagnosis using computational techniques, with a focus on feature extraction and selection techniques. We review multiple approaches to feature extraction and selection, including conventional techniques and proficient DL architectures. In addition, we discuss the challenges and opportunities associated with these techniques, as well as possible future developments in this promptly evolving field.

Keywords— Brain Tumors, machine learning, deep learning, Neuroimaging, Computer Aided Diagnosis

1. INTRODUCTION

Brain tumors pose a significant health risk globally, necessitating accurate and timely detection for effective treatment. Traditional diagnosis methods, such as visual inspection and manual segmentation, are time-consuming and subject to human error. Computer vision techniques have emerged as promising tools to automate brain tumor detection and diagnosis [1]. Cancer of the brain or central nervous system is the tenth leading cause of mortality for both men and women. Even though brain tumors are not the leading cause of death worldwide, 40% of other forms of cancer (such as lung and breast malignancies) metastatically transform into brain tumors [2]. Although the biopsy is regarded as the gold standard for cancer diagnosis, it presents a number of challenges, including low sensitivity/specificity, risk during the biopsy procedure, and relatively lengthy wait periods for biopsy results. Due to the rise in the number of patients with brain tumors, there is a need for a non-invasive, computer-aided diagnostic instrument that can accurately diagnose and estimate the grade of a tumor within a few seconds [3].

This paper provides an overview of detection and classification computational techniques, emphasizing feature extraction and selection methods, and discusses their potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy.

2. COMPUTER VISION TECHNIQUES

This section presents an overview of computational techniques employed in brain tumor detection as shown in Fig. 1. Additionally, the importance of feature selection

algorithms, such as principal component analysis (PCA), recursive feature elimination (RFE), and genetic algorithms is also discussed. Various feature extraction techniques, including intensity-based, texture-based, and shape-based features, are certainly important.

ML Computational Techniques for Brain Tumor Detection

- i. Support Vector Machines (SVM): SVMs [4] are popular for their ability to handle high-dimensional data and nonlinear classification tasks. They perform well when the decision boundary between tumor and non-tumor samples is well-defined and can capture complex patterns with the appropriate choice of kernel functions. However, SVMs may struggle with larger datasets and can be sensitive to hyperparameter tuning.
- ii. Random Forests (RF): RF [5] models are ensemble learning methods that combine multiple decision trees. They excel in handling high-dimensional data and can capture complex interactions among features. RF [6] models are robust to noise and outliers, but they may have limitations in capturing fine-grained spatial information and require careful feature selection and hyperparameter tuning.

- iii. Gradient Boosting Models [7] (e.g., XGBoost, LightGBM): Gradient boosting models iteratively train weak learners (decision trees) in a boosting framework. They can effectively handle complex interactions and nonlinearity in the data. Gradient boosting models often outperform other ML models, but they require more computational resources and longer training times. They are also sensitive to hyperparameter settings.

DL Computational Techniques for Brain Tumor Detection

DL has revolutionized medical image analysis due to their ability to learn hierarchical representations automatically. This section explores the application of deep learning techniques, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and hybrid architectures. The utilization of Transfer learning and data augmentation strategies is discussed, along with the challenges associated with training deep models with limited data.

- i. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN): CNNs [8] are widely used in computer vision tasks, including brain tumor detection. They can

automatically learn hierarchical representations and spatial patterns directly from raw pixel intensities. CNNs excel in capturing fine-grained spatial information and have demonstrated superior performance in many images analysis tasks.

- ii. U-Net: U-Net [9] is a specialized CNN architecture designed for medical image segmentation tasks. It consists of an encoding path for feature extraction and a decoding path for precise localization. U-Net is particularly effective in segmenting brain tumors by capturing detailed tumor boundaries.
- iii. Residual Networks (ResNet): ResNet [10] is a DL architecture that employs residual connections to alleviate the vanishing gradient problem. ResNet models have shown improved performance in various image classification tasks. They can capture complex and deep features, making them suitable for brain tumor detection. However, deeper ResNet models may suffer from overfitting and require regularization techniques, such as dropout or batch normalization.

Figure 1 Some examples from ML and DL computer vision techniques

Feature Extraction and Selection Methods

Feature extraction and selection play a crucial role in optimizing the performance of brain tumor detection systems. This section presents importance feature extraction methods, including wavelet transforms, local binary patterns (LBP), and histogram of oriented gradients (HOG). It also discusses feature selection techniques, such as correlation-based feature selection (CFS), mutual information-based methods, and L1 regularization. The benefits and limitations of these methods in brain tumor analysis are highlighted.

3. NEUROIMGING AND COMPUTER-AIDED DIAGNOSIS (CAD) FOR TUMOR DETECTION

Importance of Neuroimaging Techniques

Accurate and non-invasive medical imaging techniques play a vital role in the detection and diagnosis of brain tumors. Neuroimaging techniques [10], such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), provide

detailed structural and functional information about the brain. These imaging modalities enable clinicians to visualize the size, location, and characteristics of brain tumors, aiding in treatment planning and monitoring disease progression. The availability of high-quality medical images is essential for developing effective CAD systems for brain imaging analysis [11].

Significance of CAD in Neuroimaging

Computer vision [xxxxxx] systems have emerged as valuable tools in assisting radiologists and clinicians in the interpretation and analysis of medical images. CAD systems leverage ML and DL algorithms to automatically detect and classify abnormalities in medical images, including brain tumors as demonstrated in Fig. 2. The integration of CAD in brain imaging analysis offers several advantages:

- i. Increased Accuracy and Efficiency: CAD systems can analyze medical images rapidly and accurately, assisting radiologists in detecting subtle abnormalities that might be overlooked during manual inspection. By reducing the

- chances of human error and providing a second opinion, CAD systems enhance diagnostic accuracy and efficiency.
- ii. **Early Detection and Intervention:** CAD systems enable the early detection of brain tumors, potentially leading to timely interventions and improved patient outcomes. Early diagnosis allows for prompt treatment planning and monitoring, increasing the chances of successful tumor removal or effective tumor management.
 - iii. **Quantitative Analysis and Biomarker Extraction:** CAD systems facilitate quantitative analysis of medical images, extracting relevant features and biomarkers that aid in tumor characterization. These features can include shape, texture, intensity, and spatial information, providing valuable insights for tumor classification, grading, and prognosis.
 - iv. **Standardization and Consistency:** CAD systems contribute to the standardization and consistency of brain imaging analysis. By automating the analysis process, CAD systems reduce inter- and intra-observer variability, ensuring reliable and reproducible results. This standardization is particularly important in multi-center studies and longitudinal follow-up assessments.
 - v. **Workflow Optimization:** CAD systems streamline the radiology workflow by pre-analyzing medical images and highlighting suspicious regions or abnormalities. This optimization saves time for radiologists and allows them to focus on complex cases, improving overall efficiency and patient throughput.
 - vi. **Research and Clinical Decision Support:** CAD systems generate valuable data and insights that can be used for research purposes, clinical decision support systems, and treatment planning. By integrating clinical and imaging data, CAD systems can assist in personalized medicine approaches and facilitate evidence-based decision-making.
- The integration of CAD systems in brain imaging analysis enhances diagnostic accuracy, efficiency, and standardization. CAD systems play a significant role in early detection, quantitative analysis, workflow optimization, education, research, and clinical decision support, ultimately improving patient care and outcomes.

Figure 2 Demonstration of significance of Neuroimaging and AD in Brain Tumor detection and diagnosis

4. PATTERN ANALYSIS OF BRAIN IMAGES FOR TUMOR DETECTION

ML and DL approaches offer distinct perspectives and approaches to pattern analysis in brain images for tumor detection. While both techniques aim to extract meaningful features and patterns from medical images, they differ in terms of their architectural design, training process, and interpretability. This section discusses the contrasting perspectives of ML and DL in brain image analysis for tumor detection as shown in Fig. 3.

ML Perspective

ML algorithms traditionally rely on handcrafted features extracted from medical images. These features are often engineered based on domain knowledge and prior expertise. In the context of brain tumor detection, machine learning models typically employ statistical and mathematical techniques to extract and analyze these features. The key characteristics of the ML perspective include:

- a. **Feature Engineering:** ML models heavily depend on carefully engineered features, such as intensity-based, texture-based, and shape-based descriptors. These features capture relevant information related to the tumor's size, shape, texture variations, and spatial relationships with surrounding structures.
- b. **Dimensionality Reduction:** ML models often employ dimensionality reduction techniques, such as principal component analysis (PCA) [13] or feature selection algorithms, to reduce the dimensionality of the feature space. This step helps in mitigating the curse of dimensionality and improving the model's performance.
- c. **Model Selection and Training:** Various ML algorithms, including support vector machines (SVM), decision trees, random forests, and logistic regression, are commonly used for brain tumor detection. These models are trained on labeled datasets, where the input features and corresponding tumor labels are used to learn the underlying patterns and build predictive models.
- d. **Interpretable Features:** One of the advantages of ML models are their interpretability. Since handcrafted features are explicitly engineered, it is often possible to interpret the influence of each feature on the model's decision. This interpretability can aid clinicians and researchers

in understanding the underlying characteristics of brain tumors.

Figure 3 pseudocode description of ML and DL algorithms in neuroimage analysis for brain tumor detection

Deep Learning Perspective

DL techniques, on the other hand, offer a different perspective on pattern analysis in brain image analysis. DL models learn hierarchical representations directly from the raw input data without the need for explicit feature engineering. In the context of brain tumor detection, DL models can exploit the complex patterns and spatial relationships present in medical images. The key characteristics of the deep learning perspective include:

- i. End-to-End Learning: Deep learning models learn complex representations through multiple

layers of interconnected neurons. These models can automatically learn hierarchical features at different levels of abstraction, directly from the raw pixel intensities of brain images, without explicit feature engineering.

- ii. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs): CNNs are particularly effective in analyzing spatial data, making them well-suited for brain image analysis. CNNs utilize convolutional layers to learn local spatial patterns and capture higher-level features as the network deepens.

- iii. **Large-Scale Training:** DL models require a substantial amount of labeled data for training. By leveraging large-scale datasets, deep learning models can learn more generalized representations and achieve higher accuracy.
- iv. **Black-Box Nature:** One challenge of DL models is their black-box nature. While they excel in capturing complex patterns, the internal workings of deep neural networks are often difficult to interpret. This lack of interpretability can limit their adoption in certain domains where interpretability is crucial.
- v. **Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning:** DL models can benefit from transfer learning, where pre-trained models on large-scale datasets are fine-tuned on smaller brain tumor datasets. This approach allows models to leverage learned representations from other domains and adapt them to brain tumor detection tasks, even with limited labeled data.

ML Training for Feature Extraction and Selection

- i. **Feature Extraction:** In ML, feature extraction is typically performed using handcrafted features based on domain knowledge. These features are engineered beforehand and are often specific to the problem at hand, such as intensity-based, texture-based, or shape-based descriptors. Once the features are extracted, ML models are trained using the selected features.
- ii. **Feature Selection:** ML models may require feature selection techniques to reduce dimensionality and focus on the most informative features. Feature selection methods, such as correlation-based feature selection (CFS) [14], recursive feature elimination (RFE) [15], or genetic algorithms [16], can be employed to identify the most relevant features for the ML model.

DL Training for Feature Extraction and Selection

- i. **Feature Extraction:** In DL, feature extraction is an inherent part of the model training process. Instead of relying on handcrafted features, DL models learn hierarchical representations directly from raw input data, such as pixel intensities in brain images. CNNs are commonly used in DL for brain image analysis, where convolutional layers automatically learn spatial patterns and higher-level features.
- ii. **Fine-tuning and Transfer Learning:** DL models can benefit from TL, where pre-trained models on large-scale datasets (e.g., ImageNet) are utilized as a starting point. The pre-trained models have learned general image representations, which can be fine-tuned on smaller brain imaging datasets. This approach allows DL models to leverage pre-learned features and adapt them to specific brain imaging tasks, even with limited labeled data.
- iii. **Learning Optimizers and Learning Rates:** Both ML and DL models require optimization

algorithms and learning rates to train the models effectively.

Optimizers and Learning Rates

- i. **Machine Learning (ML):** models typically use optimization algorithms such as gradient descent, stochastic gradient descent (SGD), or variants like Adam, RMSprop, or AdaBoost. The learning rate determines the step size during optimization, needs to be carefully chosen to avoid convergence issues or slow learning [16].
- ii. **Deep Learning (DL):** DL models also employ optimization algorithms like SGD, Adam, or RMSprop. However, DL models often require more advanced optimization techniques due to the complexity of neural network architectures. Learning rates in DL are typically set empirically and often benefit from a decay schedule, such as reducing the learning rate gradually during training [17].

It is important to note that the selection of the optimal optimizer and learning rate for ML and DL models in brain imaging require experimentation and fine-tuning.

5. VALIDATION TECHNIQUES

- i. **Train-Test Split:** The dataset is divided into separate training and testing sets. The model is trained on the training set and evaluated on the independent testing set to assess its performance.
- ii. **Cross-Validation:** The dataset is partitioned into multiple subsets (folds), and the model is trained and tested on different combinations of these folds. This technique provides a more robust estimate of the model's performance by averaging results across multiple iterations.
- iii. **Stratified Sampling:** In the presence of imbalanced datasets (unequal tumor and non-tumor samples), stratified sampling ensures that the train-test splits or cross-validation folds maintain the original class distribution to avoid biased evaluations.
- iv. **Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV):** Each sample is used as a separate test set, while the remaining samples are used for training. This technique is especially useful for smaller datasets [18].
- v. **K-Fold Cross-Validation:** The dataset is divided into K equal-sized folds, with each fold used as a testing set while the rest act as the training set. This technique strikes a balance between LOOCV and train-test split [19] [20].
- vi. **External Validation:** The trained model is tested on an entirely independent dataset (not used during training or validation) to assess its generalization performance on unseen data.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In conclusion, ML and DL techniques have shown great potential in brain tumor detection and diagnosis. Feature extraction and selection methods significantly impact the performance of these systems. This review paper has

provided a comprehensive overview of the latest advancements in this domain, highlighting the importance of feature extraction and selection methods and identifying potential areas for future. As the field continues to evolve, several promising directions emerge. This section discusses potential future research directions, such as integrating clinical data with imaging data, developing robust deep learning models for small datasets, and exploring novel feature extraction and selection techniques. The importance of standardizing benchmark datasets and evaluation metrics is emphasized to facilitate comparison and reproducibility.

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